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THE APTITUDES OF INDUSTRIAL DESIGN STUDENTS TOWARDS ECODESIGN ACTIVITIES IN ENGINEERING COURSE

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the experiences in ecodesign activities of first semester undergraduate students in the engineering course at Chiba University. The students' concern with environmental issues and the practical works performed were analyzed and discussed. The results of the questionnaires have shown that the students believe the socio-cultural aspects have great impact on the solution of the current environmental issues. Based on the practical design works on the elements of nature (Water, Earth/Terra, Wind and Fire), the students focused on the technology (energy production and use) and social-cultural (message of natural elements) approaches.

Keywords: ecodesign, industrial design, sustainable development

INTRODUCTION

In this research the opinions and attitudes of first semester students in industrial design (Undergraduate Students of Industrial Design Courses at Chiba University) regarding environmental issues are analyzed. Their practical design works related to the elements of nature (Earth/Terra, Water, Wind and Fire) were also analyzed.

The authors' main reason for conducting this research is that sustainable issues and ecodesign practices have not yet been fully discussed in the academic industrial design course. Another reason was the little insight into the role of future industrial designers in the attainment of a more sustainable development.

The ecodesign theory class was introduced in 2007 in the graduate course at Chiba University. Year by year the numbers of students has increased for looking ecodesign class. (In 2007, the numbers of students were 50. In 2011, there were 110 students). However, ecodesign classes have not yet been included in the undergraduate course. The authors express the urgent need for implementation of an ecodesign class in the first semester of the course.

INDUSTRIAL DESIGN AND ECODESIGN IN JAPAN

As mediators between the manufacturing process and consumers, and the technical and marketing requirements, the industrial designers are obtaining key positions in many companies in areas such as new product development. This is understandable because industrial designers must have the ability to solve complex and challenging issues related to the development of design with minimal environmental impact. Industrial designers can also play a fundamental role in the definition of this new 'consumption and production scenario(s)'.

During the 20-year history of the industrial design field in Japan, the promotion of "environmental concern" and "ecology" in the design field has been initially focused on activities related to design competitions. Only recently has "sustainable design" been considered in design academic courses. (Japan Design Foundation, 1989-1995) (Green Designing in Yamagata, 1992-1997) (Ecodesign99, 1999)

The term “ecological design” in the Dictionary of Today’s Design was introduced in 1992, after many ecological design events, e.g. the “International Design Competition Osaka” (IDCO) that was based on the theme “Earth” and “Green Designing in Yamagata Competition” (GDYC).

The International Design Competition Osaka (IDCO)

The IDCO, known as the “Osaka Competition”, is a unique world bi-annual competition that attracts attention from designers around the world due to its unprecedented scale covering all areas of design, with global themes represented by Chinese characters. The award-winning works were selected by the jury based on their excellent design, as well as their social and cultural significance to the future of humankind.

The competition has been sponsored by the Japan Design Foundation (JDF) since 1983 with the basic theme “Design for Every Being”. The judges of the competition are selected with the cooperation of the ICOGRADA, the ICSID and the IFI (International Federation of Interior Architects/Interior Designers). (Japan Design Foundation, 1989-1995)

The Green Designing in Yamagata Competition (GDYC)

The GDYC is also a unique annual competition in Japan, which is especially dedicated to the environmental concern. For six years (1992-1997) it has encouraged many designers to propose innovative solutions to reduce the environmental impact in order to protect the global environment. The GDYC promoted its first competition through the media one year before the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (Earth Summit) held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in 1992. At that time, 2212 design works were submitted, a figure considerably higher than that found in similar competitions. (Green Designing in Yamagata, 1992-1997)

DESIGN OF RESEARCH

Based on the role and the activities performed by an industrial designer, one questionnaire was formulated and distributed to undergraduate students of Industrial Design Courses at the Chiba University.

In the questionnaire a total of twenty-five questions (on four pages at one side) about the environmental aspects was asked to students. The first part was related to their profiles, the second part to their personal opinion about environmental problems and the third part to their learning on environmental aspects.

The questionnaires were answered by 250 first semester undergraduate students in industrial design courses at the School of Engineering. Most of them were men aged 19-20.

The questionnaire survey and the practical works were carried out from March 2010 to April 2010.

The theme of the practical works concerned the elements of nature (Water, Earth /Terra, Wind and Fire), which was selected to stimulate the imagination and creativity based on the simple keyword. The concept of theme was based on the IDCO from 1989 to 1993.

The students were allowed to choose the themes of their interest related to the elements of nature. The works were carried out for three weeks (in a total 4,5 hours) during the practical classes of design modeling, in limited classroom space.

Students were also encouraged to explore three-dimensional forms. The maximum size of each work was 20 (height) cm x 20 cm (width) x 20 cm (length). The basic materials used were paper, wood and plastic.

99 percent of the students had no training or experience in modeling, sketching and product development.

Figure 1 The most important factor in obtaining a solution for the current environmental problems.

SURVEY RESULTS AND DESIGN WORKS

PERSONAL ATTITUDE OF STUDENTS TOWARDS OVERVIEW OF ENVIRONMENTAL ISSUES

Based on the Ecodesign Awareness Workshop of Ecodesign Manual by Brezet (Han Brezet and Carolien van Hemeland, 1997), students were asked to express their views on the environmental issue regarding four factors: technology, socio-cultural factor, economy and ecology (conservation of nature).

According to the results of this survey, the students found that the socio-cultural factors are the most decisive for the solution for the current environmental issues. Choosing the fundamental changes in individual attitudes, changes in consumer lifestyles and education factors. (Figure 1)

The current environmental education and learning from the students' view. According to Gardener (Gerald T. Gardener and Paul C. Stern, 1997) the lack of environmental information can be a serious obstacle to pro-environmental action, because it is not always obvious to the individual what he/she should do to. This is particularly true in environmental protection, because it is difficult to distinguish, based on one's personal experience, the relationship between behavior and its impact on the environment.

Based on the survey' answers, 20 percent of the students were given environmental education in the previous years (2009), and 80 percent were not given any education on environmental issues. These

1. Examples of environmentally friendly products.
2. Recycling and disassembly
3. Eco-toxic substances that are used and emitted during production of materials and components.
4. Environmental costs (for waste disposal, recycling, etc)
5. Green marketing consumerism
6. Energy conscious design of products
7. Environmental legislation
8. Environmental assessment methods
9. Other
10. Neither, I'm not interest.

Figure 2 The most important environmental topic on which students would like to receive more information.

1. Low or no environmental concern in a given industry sector
2. Poorly interface between environmental management and R+D
3. Narrowed perception of the significant environmental aspects
4. Environmental issues have no strategic relevance
5. Legislation guides goal setting
6. Low Knowledge of the environmental impact of specific products
7. Justify invested time and money for environmental program
8. I don't know
9. Cross functional characteristic of both design and environmental issues
10. Lack of methods for early planning stages
11. Evolutionary aspect of EMS (Environmental Manager System)
12. Cost-orientation instead of strategic orientation
13. Other (please specify: _____)

Figure 3. The most relevant barriers to the compliance with environmental requirements in products and services from the students' view.

affirmed they would like to receive environmental education.

The students were found to have little knowledge on environmental issues. Thirty percent of the students said they were aware of the ISO 14001 certification.

Theme	Works Frequency	Percent frequency	Categories
Water	56	22%	Message
Terra	34	14%	
Fire	73	29%	Energy
Wind	87	35%	
Total	250	100%	100%

Table 1. Analysis of the practical work (categories)

Another factor reported by the students was the unavailability of information on environmental issues at industrial design courses.

Regarding the environmental topics on which the students wanted more information, environmentally friendly products ranked first (43%), followed by recycling and disassembly (16%). (Figure 2)

Based on the classification of barriers or obstacles by Ries (G. Ries; Winkler R.Zust, 1999), thirty-eight percent of the students expressed that the main barriers to the compliance of environmental regulations by the current products and services were the little to no environmental concern in a given industry sector.

Another aspect was the low interface between environmental management and R+D (Research and Development). (Figure 3)

DESIGN WORKS

The purpose of design works was to explore the creativity of students, so that they could see by themselves the environmental factors in the theme.

The theme was very abstract, with only one Chinese character, without further details or explanations on the contents.

At first, the students had considerable difficulty with choosing the themes of their interest regarding the elements of nature: water, sun, wind and earth/terra.

After the selection of the theme, another difficulty was to devise a new concept form based on the elements of nature.

Most students had no training in modeling, nor knowledge of materials.

Figure 4. The themes of the practical works (frequency)

Figure 5. Solar Cell Building (Fire)

Figure 6. Wind Fan (Wind)

Figure 7. *The Last Terra (Earth)*

The size of work was 20 (height) cm x 20 cm (width) x 20 cm (length). The basic materials used to make the works were paper, wood and plastic.

According to the findings obtained, the works were divided into two categories. The works focused on the energy aspects (production and use) and the message (Table 1).

Those focused on the message were related to the social and cultural aspects of everyday's life and conservation of nature. As for the works focused on the energy aspects they concerned environmental technologies.

As it can be seen in Table 1, 36 percent of the students focused their attention on the product's message, which had a relationship with the water and earth/terra themes.

64 percent of the students focused on the energy conservation and use stages, which had a relationship with fire and wind.

The categories and sample groups related to the wind and fire themes were characterized by elements of evolution, like energy production and use. In this category, the solar cell panel and wind power technology were explored by students in their entry works. (Figure 5 and 6)

Figure 8. *Save Water (Water)*

The themes water and earth/terra were characterized by common elements of evolution, as the concern with the use of natural resources, reduced energy consumption, cleaner energy, zero waste emission, among others. In this category, the students were found to be familiar with the exploration of water and earth resources.

The works were focused on the message of conservation of nature and environmental issues. This is very clear in the sample works of figures 7 and 8.

DISCUSSION

As it has been shown in the survey results, the students expressed their concern with pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors to achieve a sustainable development.

Most students (80%) that were not given environmental education since the previous year stressed their interest in getting environmental education, and particularly information on examples of environmentally friendly products.

The authors found that one of the main limiting factors for their students was their little knowledge on technical problems and environmental cost aspects. Another limiting factor was their lack of experience in solving problems, and also the lack of time for research (4,5 hours).

CONCLUSIONS

In the present research, the students were found to believe that the socio-cultural factors are the most decisive for the solution of the present environmental issues, showing a pro-environmental attitude.

The students also showed a pro-environmental attitude and behavior in their design works. They explored the message of environmental concern in the themes related with water and earth/terra. The fire and wind themes were explored from the technology approach, e.g. energy production and use stage.

They suggested that there were more flexible possibilities for students to propose innovative design concepts with themes related with wind and fire. However, their little knowledge of ecodesign principles and technical problems are one of the main barriers to the proposal of concrete solutions.

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